

Measurement of ${}^9\text{Be}$ Radius via Muonic Atom Spectroscopy

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Instruction

The Research Thesis was done in the Faculty of Physics under the supervision of Prof. Ben Ohayon

Ethical Statement

The author of this thesis states that the research, including the collection, processing and presentation of data, addressing and comparing to previous research, etc., was done entirely in an honest way, as expected from scientific research that is conducted according to the ethical standards of the academic world. Also, reporting the research and its results in this thesis was done in an honest and complete manner, according to the same standards.

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List of Publications

The following publications are directly related to the work presented in this thesis:

- QUARTET collaboration introduction — Ohayon, B.; **Eizenberg, O.** *et al.* Towards Precision Muonic X-ray Measurements of Charge Radii of Light Nuclei. *Physics* **2024**, 6, 206215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/physics6010015>
- Dedicated MMC detector development — Unger, D.; **Eizenberg, O.**; *et al.* MMC Array to Study X-Ray Transitions in Muonic Atoms. *Journal of Low Temperature Physics* **2024**, 216, 344351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10909-024-03141-x>

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Abstract

The charge-radius of the nucleus is a key quantity that encodes information about the distribution of charge inside the nucleus. Precise determinations of nuclear charge radii are essential for testing *ab initio* nuclear structure theories and for constraining the fundamental interactions governing few-body systems. Nuclear radii can be extracted from elastic electron scattering, laser spectroscopy, and muonic atom spectroscopy, with the latter providing the smallest relative uncertainties. However, results from different experimental methods have not always been mutually consistent, as previously demonstrated by the proton-radius puzzle, where the charge radius extracted from muonic hydrogen disagreed with that obtained from electronic atoms via electron scattering and laser spectroscopy.

Applying muonic atom spectroscopy to light nuclei offers a direct and model-independent way to determine their charge radii, but it has been constrained by the limited efficiency and resolution of X-ray detectors. Recent advances in quantum sensing technology, particularly the development of metallic magnetic calorimeters (MMCs), now provide the necessary combination of sensitivity, linearity, and resolving power to overcome these limitations.

The QUANTum inteRacTions with Exotic aToms (QUARTET) collaboration aims to integrate MMC-based detectors into muonic atom spectroscopy experiments at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), with the goal of improving the absolute precision of charge radii for low- Z nuclei from lithium to neon. In this work, I present a measurement of the $2p \rightarrow 1s$ transition in muonic ${}^9\text{Be}$, which enables the extraction of its root-mean-square (rms) charge radius. Despite far from optimal operating conditions, including disturbances from higher substrate temperature and highly energetic Michelle electrons that affected detector stability and line shape, the transition energy was measured to be $33391.2(4)$ eV. This represents a 25-fold improvement in precision compared to previous measurements of muonic beryllium, allowing the ${}^9\text{Be}$ charge radius determined from electron scattering to be refined by approximately a factor of four.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The nuclear charge radius r_c is defined as the root-mean-square of the nuclear charge distribution. It has been extensively studied across the isotopic landscape [1]. Their precise measurement is crucial for advancing theoretical predictions in simple atomic and molecular systems, enabling tests of bound-state Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) predictions, determinations of fundamental constants, and searches for new physics [2].

As an example, nuclear theory calculations predict that the difference in radii between mirror nuclei scales with the isospin asymmetry [3]. These calculations have recently been validated by several experiments across the periodic table [4]. Nevertheless, agreement in the sparsely explored region of high asymmetry values, $\frac{N-Z}{N+Z} > 0.13$, remains limited due to the relatively large uncertainties in the radii of light nuclei, such as Li, Be, and B. In particular, the uncertainty in the radii of the entire beryllium isotope chain is constrained by that of ${}^9\text{Be}$, since the isotopic differences were extracted relative to ${}^9\text{Be}$ with high precision [5]. A high-precision measurement of the ${}^9\text{Be}$ charge radius would, therefore, extend the comparison between experiment and theory and hold the potential to reveal new physics.

Charge radii and their isotopic variations can be probed through several electromagnetic methods [6], including optical transitions [7], K-x-ray measurements [8], muonic-atom spectroscopy [9], and electron scattering [10]. The current precision status of light-nucleus charge radii is summarized in Figure 1.1. It is evident that the lowest precision radii occurs in the low- Z regime, just above helium. This region is currently out of reach for the laser spectroscopy of muonic atoms approach, and the properties of germanium-based spectrometers make them unsuitable for high-precision muonic x-ray spectroscopy.

Muonic atom x-ray spectroscopy is the employment of hydrogen-like light muonic ions, in which a negative muon replaces all the electrons, serving as an extremely sensitive probe of nuclear structure. The enhanced sensitivity is due to the muon mass being 200 times larger than that of the electron. Precision spectroscopy of transitions involving s-states can be used to extract radii. In addition to this enhanced sensitivity, muonic transitions typically lie in the hard x-ray energy domain, where high-resolution detectors can be developed and well-calibrated reference lines are readily available.

Although Metallic Magnetic Calorimeters (MMCs) were first more than two decades ago, recent advances in cryogenic detector technology have dramatically improved their performance, enabling their use as state-of-the-art spectrometers. MMCs are microcalorimeters that operate at millikelvin temperatures and measure the temperature rise caused by the absorption of individual photons. Compared to conventional solid-state detectors, MMCs offer superior energy resolution at low photon energies and a better linear response over a broad dynamic range. These properties are particularly advantageous for the measurement of hard x-rays and soft gamma rays, making MMCs a natural choice for high-precision charge-radius measurements of low- Z nuclei.

This thesis summarizes the work that I have done on the muonic atom energies of ^9Be within the framework of the QUARTET collaboration, an international effort whose central ambition is to close the precision gap for the charge radii of the low- Z nuclei. QUARTET combines muonic atom spectroscopy with custom-made MMC detectors. This thesis is organized as follows: Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background on nuclear charge radii, muonic atoms, and the principles of x-ray detection using MMCs. Chapter 3 introduces the experimental setup of the 2024 QUARTET Campaign at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), along with data acquisition. Focusing on beryllium-9, Chapter 4 summarizes the methods of data processing, spectrum analysis, and the extraction of the charge radius. Finally, Chapter 5 summarizes the findings, discusses their implications for nuclear physics, and provides an outlook for future work. Additional aspects of the data analysis, including peak identification and the detection of detector flux jumps, are presented in Appendices 2 and 3.

Figure 1.1: Fractional uncertainties of charge radii for selected light nuclei [11]. The poorest-known precision cases lie in the low- Z region just above helium. Colors indicate the type of experiment: Orange—muonic atoms laser spectroscopy; Light green—elastic electron scattering; Dark green—muonic atom x-ray spectroscopy using double-crystal spectrometer; Light blue—muonic atom x-ray spectroscopy using germanium detectors.

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter provides the theoretical background necessary to understand the measurement of the ${}^9\text{Be}$ nuclear charge radius via muonic atom spectroscopy.

2.1 Muonic Atoms Spectroscopy

2.1.1 Formation of Muonic atoms

Today, muons are produced in accelerator facilities such as LAMPF (Los Alamos) or PSI (Villigen) in high-flux beams. Upon hitting a target, the muons slow down and are captured by the atoms of the target material. Bound muons are initially captured in a high-energy state and subsequently de-excite through a cascade of transitions to lower energy levels, releasing Auger electrons, followed by the emission of characteristic muonic x-rays. Ultimately, the muon either decays, producing a Michel electron, or is captured by the nucleus. During this process, the electrons might also emit x-rays and cause the release of Auger electrons.

Figure 2.1: Schematic drawing of the muon cascade process with the electron-muon configuration evolution in an atom inspired by [12]. Muonic energy levels are presented in blue while electronic energy levels are presented in red. All scales are arbitrary and not all energy levels are plotted..

2.1.2 Muonic atoms and radii

The spectrum of muonic x-rays from the cascade corresponds to the difference in energy levels of a bound state of a nucleus with a single muon—a hydrogen-like muonic atom. First, the energy levels can be roughly calculated using the Schrödinger equation

$$E_n = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{R_\infty Z^2 m_\mu}{n^2 m_e}, \quad (2.1)$$

where R_∞ is the Rydberg constant, Z is the proton number, and $m_{\mu,e}$ are the masses of the muon and electron. The energies emitted by muonic atoms are significantly larger and are in the hard x-ray region. A more accurate calculation can be performed using the relativistic Dirac's equation (ΔE_D) while taking into account leading-order corrections from QED (δE_{QED}), nuclear polarization effects (δE_{NP}), and finite nuclear size corrections (δE_{FNS}). It may be expressed as a sum

$$\Delta E = \Delta E_D + \delta E_{\text{QED}} + \delta E_{\text{FNS}} + \delta E_{\text{NP}}. \quad (2.2)$$

with

$$\delta E_{\text{FNS}} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{(Z\alpha)^4 \mu^3}{n^3} \delta_{l0} r_c^2, \quad (2.3)$$

that only contributes to S -states. For sub-leading terms, see e.g. Ref. [13]. The proportionality to Z and μ makes the radius sensitivity significantly higher in muonic atom spectroscopy compared to electronic atoms. The radius sensitivity factor may be written as

$$\frac{\delta E}{\delta r_c} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{(Z\alpha)^4 \mu^3 \delta_{l0} r_c}{n^3}. \quad (2.4)$$

To improve the fractional accuracy of r_c in $\mu^9\text{Be}$ from its current value of 1% it is required to measure an $np \rightarrow 1s$ transition to better than ≈ 2 eV. See also Figure 1.1.

In such levels of accuracy, it is required to take into account the fine and hyperfine structure; it was calculated by Dr. Shikha Rathi of the Technion group using the MCDHFGME code developed by Indelicato and Desclaux [14], and the results are summarized in Figure 2.2 and Table 2.1. Each line has a natural linewidth due to the lifetime of the initial state, which can be estimated by mass and charge scaling from electronic hydrogen linewidth [15]

$$\Gamma_{2 \rightarrow 1}(Z) \approx Z^4 \Gamma_{2 \rightarrow 1}(H) \frac{m_\mu}{m_e}. \quad (2.5)$$

For $\mu^9\text{Be}$, the natural linewidth ≈ 0.02 eV and will therefore be assumed to be negligible later.

Figure 2.2: Left: schematic drawing of the Schrödinger calculated band-structure. The energy values are respectively to the ground-state. Middle: zoom-in on the hyperfine-structure of the $2 \rightarrow 1$ transition scaled in energy. Each line represents a state whose quantum numbers are defined as follows; n connected to the band on the left side by a dashed line, J is stated on the intersection before splitting, F is stated on the right side of each line. The arrows in the HFS illustrate the allowed transitions ($> 1\%$ intensity) of the muon. The thickness of the arrow is scaled with the intensity of the transition. Right: simulated peak for the transition assuming FWHM of 20 eV of a detector.

Table 2.1: Positions relative to the center-of-gravity and intensities of the calculated hyperfine lines of ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ peak (sorted by descending intensity).

$(J_i, F_i) \rightarrow (J_f, F_f)$	Relative Position [eV]	Intensity (%)
$(3/2, 3) \rightarrow (1/2, 2)$	2.356	29.17
$(3/2, 2) \rightarrow (1/2, 2)$	1.942	11.50
$(1/2, 2) \rightarrow (1/2, 1)$	-4.133	11.50
$(1/2, 1) \rightarrow (1/2, 2)$	0.012	11.47
$(3/2, 1) \rightarrow (1/2, 1)$	-1.516	11.46
$(3/2, 2) \rightarrow (1/2, 1)$	-2.021	9.33
$(1/2, 2) \rightarrow (1/2, 2)$	-0.170	9.34
$(3/2, 0) \rightarrow (1/2, 1)$	-1.029	4.17
$(3/2, 1) \rightarrow (1/2, 2)$	2.447	1.03
$(1/2, 1) \rightarrow (1/2, 1)$	-3.951	1.03

2.2 MMC Detectors

An MMC is a type of calorimeter that uses a paramagnetic sensor. Operating at cryogenic temperatures, an MMC determines the energy of an incident particle by measuring the temperature change caused by its energy deposition in the detector's absorbing material. Several reviews cover the physics and applications of MMCs in detail [16, 17, 18]. This section provides a short overview of their operating principle. MMCs are conceptually comprised of a particle absorber with heat capacity C and a paramagnetic temperature sensor, both of which are coupled to a thermal bath. After being hit by an incident particle that deposits energy E in the absorber, it is heated by ΔT .

$$\Delta T = C^{-1} \Delta E$$

A rise in the temperature of the absorber, whose magnetization M is temperature-dependent, creates a magnetic flux change that is measured by the SQUID. The temperature stabilizes back to the thermal bath temperature. The SQUID measures changes in the magnetic flux Φ according to Eq 2.6.

$$\Delta \Phi \propto \frac{\delta M}{\delta T} \Delta T = \frac{\delta M}{\delta T} \frac{\Delta E}{C} \quad (2.6)$$

The absorber materials that are currently most used for MMCs are paramagnetic alloys of silver or gold doped with a few hundred ppm of erbium. Nowadays, such detectors are being developed for a variety of applications while optimizing them individually for the expected operating conditions. State-of-the-art MMCs optimized for the detection of soft x-ray photons, called maXs detectors, have achieved an instrumental resolution of $\Delta E_{\text{FWHM}} = 1.58$ eV while measuring ^{55}Fe [19].

2.3 Concept of the QUARTET experiments

The QUARTET collaboration seeks to extend the precision frontier of muonic-atom spectroscopy for light nuclei. By combining the high resolving power of MMC detectors with controlled muon-beam settings, the experiment aims to reach ppm-level sensitivity for the dominant $2 \rightarrow 1$ muonic transitions across the light-element region.

Achieving such sensitivity requires overcoming key challenges in detector deployment near a high-intensity muon beam, including exposure to energetic Michel electrons and the limited active area of the detector. QUARTET addresses these issues through beam-compatible data analysis steps.

Chapter 3

Experiment

The aim of the 2024 QUARTET collaboration campaign was to significantly improve the precision of the charge radii of ${}^6,7\text{Li}$, ${}^9\text{Be}$, and ${}^{10,11}\text{B}$ through muonic atom x-ray spectroscopy. Their muonic $2 \rightarrow 1$ transition energies lie at 19, 33, and 52 keV, respectively. The precision target requires a measurement accuracy of up to ≈ 2 ppm for these energies. Before starting the measurement, the detector was deployed at the PSI facility, characterized, and optimized in the staging area. In this chapter, the site, the experimental setup, and the data acquisition are described.

3.1 PSI-PiE1.2 facility

PSI is a large-scale muon-producing facility located in Villigen, Switzerland. Muons are produced as a result of high-energy proton beam hitting a graphite target, where pions are generated and later decay into muons. Magnetic fields transport the muons to dedicated beamlines. The QUARTET experiment is located in an area called PiE1.2. The muon flux in PiE1.2 varies in the range $10^3 - 10^4 \text{ mA}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ when scanning momenta in the range $15 - 45 \text{ MeV}/c$ respectively. This flux momentum relation is depicted in Figure 3.1.

3.2 Experimental Set-Up

The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 3.2 and is described in detail in a sketch in Figure 3.3. Each muon in the beam is tagged in a coincidence-scintillator counter and then hits a 45° angled beryllium target. The detector's absorber is placed so that it creates a right-angle with the target and the muon-beam. Calibration of radioactive sources and XRF-irradiated targets are placed between the target and the detector's window.

Figure 3.1: The flux-momentum relation in the PiE1.2 beamline [20]. Presented in units of muons per second per mA^{-1} of the proton beam. The nominal current of the proton beam is 2.2 mA [21, 22].

3.2.1 MMC detector

The detector module used for QUARTET is an MMC-based detector array that is described in [24] - maXs 30-v2b. The detector is composed of 20 μm thick gold absorbers divided into 64 pixels. Aluminum bonding wires connect the PCB to the eight front-end SQUIDs that are glued to a copper platform. The pixel sum corresponds to an active area of 16 mm^2 . It is placed inside a dilution fridge cryostat to create optimized operating conditions at a temperature of ≈ 20 mK. Each pair of pixels is read out together and is referred to as a channel. Each channel is connected to the same ADC. The pixels are identified such that each channel has one pixel with positive polarity and one with negative polarity. This way, the detector has 32 channels sampled by ADC1 through ADC32. Each channel has both negatively and positively polarized components, denoted as POSP and NEGP. The 4 most external channels are designed with asymmetric absorbers, making them much more temperature-sensitive: ADC1, ADC9, ADC17, and ADC25. ADC 14, 15, and 16 are used to sample auxiliary detectors, so all readings are sampled through the same ADC module. ADC3 was turned off due to high noise during beamtime.

3.2.2 Target And Calibration

The beryllium target is a high-purity 2.5 mm disk with the maximum chemical contamination limits listed in Table 1.1. It was held inside the vacuum chamber by a plastic target holder from above, as can be seen in 3.5. To calibrate the energy axis, additional sources have been inserted. Optimizing for the closest energy lines to the

Figure 3.2: A photo of the experimental set-up in the beamtime with main features are numbered: 1- Muons from the beamline pass through an entrance scintillator, 2- The cryostat in which the sidearm 3.4 holding the MMC, 3- The target holder 3.5 inserted from above to the right position forming a 90 degrees angle between the muon beam and the cryostat's sidearm, 4- HPGe detector used for beam tuning 5- The detector's electronics and readout.

Figure 3.3: A sketch of the experimental set-up during the beryllium-9 measurement [23]. In the calibration-source spot were present ^{55}Fe and ^{241}Am radioactive sources, together with x-ray fluorescence on a mixed barium and lanthanum target 3.6

Figure 3.4: Photos of the inner cryostat arm (left) and the detectors module with the 64 pixels of gold absorber (right) [25].

region of interest and for lines with the smallest energy uncertainty. For close energy-calibration, a mixed barium and lanthanum target was irradiated using an x-ray tube. ^{241}Am and ^{55}Fe sources were also inserted to be used for data-analysis as high-energy and low-energy, high statistics peaks. The calibration sources and the XRF target are shown in Fig. 3.6. Using these sources and XRF, we expect the lines summarized in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Expected x-ray and gamma lines in the experiment, ordered by descending energy. The region of interest is highlighted in bold. Lines marked with * are strong but their uncertainty is omitted since the detector described in this thesis has no resolving power for the line-structure reported in literature.

Source	Peak	Energy [keV]
Am-241	$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{(2,0)}$	59.5409(1) [26] or 59.5393(4) [27]
La	La : $K_{\alpha 1}$	33.4421(3) [28]
$^9_{\mu}\text{Be}$	$2p \rightarrow 1s$	33.40(1) [29]
Am-241	$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{(1,0)}$	33.1963(2) [30] or 33.1947(4) [27]
La	La : $K_{\alpha 2}$	33.0344(3) [28]
Ba	Ba : $K_{\alpha 1}$	32.19326(7) [28]
Ba	Ba : $K_{\alpha 2}$	31.81662(6) [28]
Am-241	$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{(2,1)}$	26.3446(2) [26]
Fe-55	Mn : K_{β} 's	6.49*
Fe-55	Mn : K_{α} 's	5.90*

Figure 3.5: The target holder of the beryllium and the boron targets. The target holder is made of plastic and holding the beryllium disk.

3.2.3 Beam Momentum Calibration

The beam momentum decision process was a tradeoff of several effects aimed at optimizing the strongest muonic signal. According to Figure 3.1, as momentum increases, the beam flux also increases. However, the muons are also captured deeper in the target, and fewer muonic x-rays manage to leave it. In addition, the higher muon-flux also inflicts a higher electron rate over the detector due to the presence of more Michel electrons. These energetic electrons may overwhelm our detector.

Figure 3.6: The sources holder is made of copper and pinned to its destined position between the vacuum chamber and the MMC. From the top clockwise; ^{55}Fe source, ^{241}Am plastic disks shielded with iron, barium and lanthanum in the XRF irradiation position and another site for ^{241}Am plastic disks shielded with iron.

For Beryllium, the chosen momentum was $29.5 \text{ MeV}/c$ due to reaching the limit rate of events at the detector.

3.3 Data Analysis

3.3.1 Data Acquisition

The MMC channels (ADCs, digitizing the signals of the SQUID readout of the MMCs) are connected via network cables to a computer on which data acquisition is performed using PAQS, a program specifically developed for MMC-based detectors [31]. PAQS controls and configures the ADC through a graphical user interface, which is used to set the ADC parameters and start measurements. A detailed description of PAQS and its software architecture can be found in the corresponding work [31]. Other detectors were also used during the beamtime for monitoring and metadata, such as room-temperature thermometers, scintillators, and HPGe detectors. The recording of their data was performed by the MIDAS data acquisition system [32].

3.3.2 Waveform analysis

The signals from the MMC-based detector are saved as triggered events. Each channel is constantly sampling at a rate of 100 MHz , including an overlap of 16-bit oversampling between samples. Channels are individually triggered when the signal crosses a user-defined threshold. Upon triggering, a trace is saved, consisting of $2^{14} = 16384$ samples, of which 4096 samples occur before the trigger and the remaining 16384 samples occur after it. Out of the saved triggered events, the Mn x-rays have been identified. These are used to generate a template of the pulse shape for a photonic event. This template is depicted in Figure 3.7 and is characterized by a rapidly rising voltage as the pulse hits,

Figure 3.7: A triggered-event trace of a photon hitting a positive pixel, the amplitude, the pretrigger, and the time of the trigger are fitted, and the χ^2 and coincidences information are calculated.

followed by a slower decay back to normal. Then, the entire dataset of triggered events is fitted using the generated template, with amplitude, time, and pretrigger offset as free parameters. Each fit result is an entry of a data file. This data file is the input for this analysis. Each data entry includes several headers; the fitted free parameter results and the χ^2 of the goodness of the fit. More magnitudes are calculated, such as muon-coincidence information and electron-coincidence information. Coincidence information is referred to as the time difference between a signal and the previous signal; e.g, muon-coincidence is the time to the last muon hit in the scintillator.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, the results from the measurement of the $\mu^9\text{Be} : 2p \rightarrow 1s$ are described. First, a presentation of the pre-processed spectrum from the entire beam time is provided, including the preceding $\mu^6\text{Li}$ and $\mu^{55}\text{Mn}$ measurements and the following $\mu^{10,11}\text{B}$ measurement. This part is also accompanied by an appendix that includes an extensive peak recognition process for the $\mu^9\text{Be}$ measured spectrum. Next, the primary steps used to process the data are described. These are the four main signal-processing steps illustrated in the flowchart in Figure 4.1, three corrections applied to the analyzed waveform data, and one step applied to the processed spectrum:

1. **Detector temperature correction** - pulse amplitudes are highly sensitive to the detector temperature. Since the temperature is unstable, the pulse height inaccurately estimates the energy of the incident photon. Correcting this effect is crucial for achieving good energy resolution.
2. **Trigger time alignment** - In order to separate the muonic signal from the calibration signal, the time between a muon-induced trigger in the scintillator and the photon induced trigger that hit the pixel is used. The detector is a combination of 64 nearly independent pixels, and the pixels share the same ADC. However, the time it takes for a pulse to rise until it crosses the voltage threshold for identification slightly differs between pixels. Aligning the timing of the various pixels is useful for improving the separation of the coincident and anticoincident signals.
3. **Nonlinear gain correction and folding** - The detector properties are not entirely linear with respect to temperature. Thus, we introduce a nonlinear gain of the pulse-height with incident energy. To achieve high precision, it is necessary to correct this issue. This step also aligns the pixels.
4. **Lineshape fitting** - The peaks that appear on the measured spectrum are a convolution of the natural lineshape with the response function of the detector. Using several peaks, a consistent response function for all the peaks is fitted.

To optimize the quality of each correction, each step includes several data-selection measures. After all the corrections, the data is ready to determine the line shape of the detector in order to extract the desired magnitude. Thus, this chapter describes the four steps of the analysis, along with the cuts that are used. After these steps, the energy difference between $\mu^9\text{Be} : 2p \rightarrow 1s$ and $\text{La} : K_{\alpha 1}$ can be extracted using the $\text{La} : K_{\alpha 1}$ literature value from [28] for the final linear calibration of the energy-axis. This energy difference is used to extract the energy of the $\mu^9\text{Be} : 2p \rightarrow 1s$ transition, which is utilized to calculate the charge-radius of ^9Be .

Figure 4.1: The main analysis steps described in this chapter are marked in purple boxes with their inputs in pink boxes. The final step where the process requires further nuclear theory calculations to achieve high accuracy.

4.1 Measurement overview

The 2024 Quartet beam time aimed to determine the absolute radii of $^{6,7}\text{Li}$, ^9Be , $^{10,11}\text{B}$, and a proof-of-concept experiment intended to observe x-rays of the $2s - 2p$ Lamb shift in Mn. Thus, focusing at the energy range between $\mu^{6,7}\text{Li} : 2p \rightarrow 1s \approx 18.6\text{keV}$ to $\mu^9\text{Be} : 2p \rightarrow 1s \approx 33.4\text{keV}$ and $\mu^{10,11}\text{B} : 2p \rightarrow 1s \approx 53.2\text{keV}$. The duration of data collection was 10 days, from October 6 to October 16, as shown in Figure 4.2. Focusing on the beryllium segment that can be seen in Figure 4.2, the duration of the stable part was a day and a half between the 11th and 12th of October. The steps described in this chapter utilize the various peaks in the measured spectrum and are already predicted in Table 3.1. Most of the measured spectrum is presented as a histogram of the post-processed data in Figure 4.3. The identification of the measured peaks and their sources is broadly covered in Appendix 2. The parts of the spectrum used in this chapter are marked in the shaded gray area. In increasing energy order; the first and third are used for trigger time alignment because this step requires high statistics of the muonic peak; the second is the region of interest with the Ba and La x-rays and the muonic-Be overlapping with the La, and the fourth is used for the temperature correction because it's the most energetic, high statistics, distinct peak. The measured spectrum includes many other peaks; the main peaks of interest are recognized, along with peaks identified as contaminations in the measurement, such as μC , μN , μO lines. By means of calculations and a literature review, it was validated that the contaminants do not appear to be hidden beneath the lines of interest.

Figure 4.2: Roughly calibrated pulse-height distributions vs. time. Events coincident ($t < 10\mu s$) with the muon trigger counter are in red. They stem predominantly from photons emitted in the muon cascade. Events detected outside this time window ($t > 20\mu s$) are depicted in blue. They originate mostly from the continuously-running calibration sources. Below each segment, appear the target and the calibrations sources used in the same time. The Ag-Mo and Ba-La non-radioactive metal targets are irradiated with XRF.

Figure 4.3: Overview of the measured spectrum. Grey-shaded areas mark the areas used in analysis, in increasing energy-order: 1) ≈ 6 keV area; $\text{Mn} - K_{\alpha,\beta}$ and ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 2$. 2) ≈ 32 keV area; $\text{Ba} - K_{\alpha}$, $\text{La} - K_{\alpha}$ and ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$. 3) ≈ 39 keV area; ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 1$. 4) ≈ 60 keV area; ${}^{241}\text{Am}$. The spectrum plotted is after all analysis steps and separated into coincident spectrum and anti-coincident spectrum based on the calculated trigger: 750 ns coincidence interval for the coincident spectrum.

Step 1: Temperature Correction

The amplitude fitted to a pulse inaccurately estimates the incident energy deposited in the detector due to its temperature variations. For times when the detector was hotter, the amplitude is fitted to a lower value, and vice versa. The challenge here is to understand the amplitude-temperature dependence in the most precise manner. Such corrections require knowledge of the detector's temperature.

- **Temperature information** - The temperature is sampled in 3 channels; ADC1, ADC9 and ADC25. These channels are designed to be more temperature sensitive than all other channels. Sampling the voltage of these channels is an estimate of the detector substrate temperature. In order to optimize the temperature estimation, several cuts are introduced. The first cut is for the coincidence of electrons hitting the detector. When an electron hits the detector, it heats up all the pixels, causing the subsequent temperature readings to be unreliable. To avoid this effect, the experiment was designed to maintain a relatively low rate of electron hits. Consequently, the initial choice to exclude temperature readings after each electron hit was set to about 10% of the total data window corresponding to approximately 50 milliseconds, as shown in Figure 4.4. Later, optimizing for the end-result, it was raised to 100 milliseconds. All channels are cut for outliers, as can be seen in Figure 4.5. With this cut, the remaining data has the most stable and continuous temperature information. However, channel ADC1 is more stable than the others and is thus chosen for correction. The other two are used to identify jumps in the selected channel. The jump identification process is summarized in Appendix 3. A jump in ADC1 was identified on October 11th at 9:30 a.m.; therefore, the correction is split at this time. A good practice to ensure that the temperature information is as clean as possible is to use a filter based on deviations from the time-averaged ADC1 information, as depicted in Figure 4.6.
- **Amplitude information** - The amplitudes of interest are the photonic amplitudes. The photon-pulses most sensitive to temperature variations are the most energetic ones. For this measurement, the americium peak at 60keV will be used. To select the photons, several cuts have been applied. Since the template for the trace fitting was generated from hand-picked photon events, photonic events are highly correlated with small χ^2 values. In Figure 4.7, not-normalized χ^2 as a function of measured amplitude, several photonic peaks can be seen as vertical lines of high-density of events. Thus, to filter the photons, a χ^2 -value-based cut is set as the dashed lines plotted in Figure 4.7, based on user-defined values for each pixel. Another effect that can lead to inaccurate amplitude reconstruction is pile-up, the occurrence of two photons hitting the detector within a short time interval. In such cases, the amplitude of the later photon may be poorly

Figure 4.4: Histogram of the time interval between a temperature read to the most recent electron hit. The cut value is marked in a vertical dashed red line.

Figure 4.5: Demonstration of the temperature behavior over time, the outliers cut are marked in dashed black lines.

Figure 4.6: Additional cut of the temperature information based on the deviation from the time-averaged temperature information. The local average value was calculated in 30 minutes running window, the deviation value was set to 0.02 V.

fitted due to its overlap with the decaying tail of the preceding pulse. Since the expected photon rate per pixel is relatively low, an initial cut was applied to exclude events occurring within 1s of a previous hit, as illustrated in Figure 4.8. Following the optimization of the analysis, this time window was subsequently reduced to 450ms. Note that the two mentioned cuts partially overlap because pileup-events will most of the time result in bad- χ^2 values too. Another cut was applied, a Gaussian smoothing filter for the time evolution of the peak amplitude, and outliers that deviated significantly from the time-averaged peak center were excluded, as shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.7: χ^2 -value as a function of amplitude for pixel ADC2-NEGP, the cut's upper limit is marked in green line and lower limit is marked in red line.

- **Correction** - The dependence of the amplitude on temperature can now be calculated. Taking into account the different pixels and the temperature jumps. Each pixel was divided into two time intervals with respect to the jump, the amplitude and temperature information are plotted for one time interval on a graph. Using a linear fit, the dependence is calculated and denoted as $A(T) = mT + n$, with A representing the amplitude and T representing the temperature. It can be seen, for example, in Figure 4.10. Using Eq. 4.1, the entire data set is corrected, where \bar{T} is arbitrarily chosen as the median of the temperature information. Later, each interval's data is fitted with a Gaussian for the americium peak and scaled to merge the pixels back to one time-series.

$$\tilde{A}(T) = A \cdot \frac{\bar{T} + n/m}{T + n/m} \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.8: Histogram of the time from the pulse-hit to the last photon hit in units of seconds. The cut value is marked in a vertical red dashed line. The dark-gray shaded area is the histogram after applying the χ^2 -based cut from Figure 4.7. The peaks in high frequencies are associated with Wi-Fi or cellular interference.

Figure 4.9: Cut of the amplitude information based on the deviation from the time-averaged peak center presented for ADC2-NEGP. The local average value was calculated in 30 minutes running window, the deviation value was set to 50 eV.

Step 2: Align Muonic Triggers per Pixel

In the experiment, a scintillator was installed and sampled between the beam's output and the target. The closest scintillator event to each pulse is assigned. The time difference between them is referred to here as 'muonic-trigger'. The muonic-trigger enables the separation of the signal to coincident with the muons and anticoincident with the muons. The coincident signal consists mostly of muonic-signal, while the anticoincident consists of calibration and noise. However, the separation is not perfect. Narrowing the coincident trigger window cleans the signal in the coincident spectrum. The muonic-trigger depends on the time it takes for a trigger to initiate sampling in each pixel. It is different for each pixel due to varying resistances and, thus, different rise-times of the pulses. Overall, the timing of the pixels differs. Using user-identified muonic peaks, the coincidence-window can be further optimized. In the ${}^9\text{Be}$ data, the most distinct and strong muonic lines are ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 2$ and ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 1$. Their trigger information is fitted with a Gaussian and then shifted to zero to align all the pixels. This process is depicted in Figure 4.11

Figure 4.10: The robust linear fit for the data of ADC2-NEGP after the jump in gray dots with the linear fit in red line. The fit was performed using the RLM method from Statsmodels [33], with the TrimmedMean norm from the statsmodels.robust.norms module.

Step 3: Pixel Nonlinearity Correction

Due to the temperature dependence of each pixels physical properties, the gain is not perfectly linear with temperature. This effect can be corrected using a quadratic transformation of each pixels spectrum. This step is also used to fold the spectra of all pixels onto one another, thus applying a consistent quadratic transformation to align them to common values.

To achieve this correction, three spectral regions are fitted:

1. the region of interest containing the La : K and Ba : K doublets,
2. the 59.4 keV ^{241}Am peak, and
3. the 26.3 keV ^{241}Am peak.

For each of these peaks, an initial fit is performed on the spectrum obtained by combining data from all pixels. This global fit is used to determine the overall shape of each region. Later, this shape is applied to fit each pixel individually with fewer degrees of freedom. An example of the fit using all-pixel data for the La and Ba region is shown in Figure 4.13. The fit models the peaks' shape in this region using the functional form presented later in Equation 4.3.

One assumption made here is that the uncertainties of the Ba and La doublet peaks are correlated. Therefore, each doublet is treated as a single peak, using one centroid parameter, while the other centroid is calculated using the literature value

ADC2 NEGP

Figure 4.11: The muonic-peaks identified and used in the ^9Be data for trigger information in ADC2-NEGP. Top row shows the muonic peaks spectra emphasizing the no background noise in the area. Bottom row shows the muonic-trigger times of the selected data used to align to be around 0. Energy units in this graph are almost keV since spectrum is not yet calibrated.

Figure 4.12: A histogram of the time after muon trigger for all photons. Presented before and after the pixel-timing alignment process described in this chapter, in blue and red correspondingly. The peak around zero, which correspond to muon-induced events, is visibly thinner after the alignment than the one before it the blue around approximately $7\mu\text{s}$

for the energy difference between the two lines from [28]. Using the results of this global fit and the same procedure for the two ^{241}Am peaks, each pixel is then fitted individually. An example of ADC2-NEGP is shown in Figure 4.14a, where the fit successfully reproduces the shape in the region of interest.

Finally, for each pixel, the measured amplitude is calibrated against the expected centroid energies from Table 3.1, denoted by E . The measured amplitude, A , is fitted to a quadratic function,

$$E(A) = m(A + nA^2), \quad (4.2)$$

from which the nonlinearity coefficient n is determined. In this way, the spectrum of each pixel is scaled using a quadratic transformation that accounts for its individual nonlinearity.

It is assumed that the La-doublet uncertainty is zero and will be included later in the final calibration analysis. For the Ba doublet and the ^{241}Am peaks, their uncertainties are also considered negligible compared to the statistical uncertainty for each pixel. An example of the quadratic calibration for ADC2-NEGP is shown in Figure 4.14b. Although this graph appears nearly linear, it includes a small but measurable nonlinearity. The extracted nonlinearity parameters, n , along with their uncertainties for all pixels, are shown in Figure 4.15. The values are small but are comparable to those reported in [34, 35]. Direct comparison is difficult; however, since uncertainties are not

reported in those references, the degree of nonlinearity varies among detectors.

The quadratic scaling described here also serves to align the pixel spectra, accounting for the different nonlinear responses of individual pixels. The calibration brings the main peaks to their literature energy values for consistency and ease of interpretation. However, this alignment could also be performed without relying on literature values by referencing any single pixel or by using the global fits presented in Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: Fit of anticoincident spectrum in the region of interest. The shape deduced by this fit is used to fit the spectrum of each pixel. The fit is on smaller bins than presented. Energy units in this graph are almost keV since spectrum is not yet calibrated.

Step 4: Lineshape Fitting and Result

The peaks of interest are measured in their natural lineshape, convoluted with the response function of the detector. The anticoincident and coincident spectra are fitted with a decreasing number of free parameters and increasing assumptions incorporated into the fitted shape logic, as explained later. At last, the energy difference between the La : $K \rightarrow L3$ and the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ is reflected in the results of the fits. Importantly, the final result does not depend on the fitting method within the calculated uncertainty margins.

The coincident spectrum will contain mostly muon-induced photons, and the anti-coincident spectrum will mostly contain photons from the calibration sources. However, there is weak calibration signal that is coincident with the muon and very weak muonic signal that is anti-coincident with the muon due to imperfect coincidence assignment. Thus, before fitting any of the spectra, knowledge about the other is required. Since the anticoincident spectrum is expected to have less muonic signal, a rough fit will be done.

Figure 4.14: (a) Fitting the lanthanum, barium and americium peaks in the measured by ADC2-NEGP assuming literature-based distance between $K \rightarrow L2$ to $K \rightarrow L3$ with zero uncertainty for both lanthanum and barium. (b) Using the results, calculate the nonlinearity of ADC2-NEGP with a quadratic fit. Error bars in the x-axis are plotted, but too small to notice. Energy units in this graph are almost keV since spectrum is not yet calibrated.

Figure 4.15: The nonlinear parameter n from the equation $E(A) = m(A + n \cdot A^2)$ used for the calibration of 35 pixels. Uncertainties were calculated using Monte Carlo taking into account statistical uncertainties of all the peaks. In this plot they are compared with similar results from Daniel Unger’s Thesis [D.U] [35] and Joshua Geist’s Thesis [J.G] [34]

The anticoincident spectrum fit results will be used to fit the coincident spectrum.

Fitting a peak is performed using the Hypermet function written in Eq. 4.3 and presented in Figure 4.16. A peak has 4 main parameters: Amplitude - A , Centroid - E_0 , gaussian FWHM - $\Gamma_G = 2\sigma\sqrt{2\log(2)}$, lorentzian FWHM - Γ_L , and 5 tail parameters: right and left tail components - f_{rt} or f_{lt} , right and left tail scales - b_{rt} or b_{lt} and the step component - f_{step} . Each fit will include 1 constant background parameter.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(E) = A & \left[f_{\text{voigt}} \cdot V(E - E_0, \Gamma_G, \Gamma_L) \right. \\
 & + \frac{f_{rt}}{2b_{rt}} \exp\left(\frac{E - E_0}{b_{rt}} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2b_{rt}^2}\right) \cdot \text{erfc}\left(\frac{E - E_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} + \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{2}b_{rt}}\right) \\
 & + \frac{f_{lt}}{2b_{lt}} \exp\left(\frac{E_0 - E}{b_{lt}} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2b_{lt}^2}\right) \cdot \text{erfc}\left(\frac{E_0 - E}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} + \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{2}b_{lt}}\right) \\
 & \left. + \frac{f_{\text{step}}}{2} \cdot \text{erfc}\left(\frac{E - E_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right) \right] \quad (4.3)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4.1 Anticoincident Fits

To include the weak muonic signal leftover in the anticoincident fit, a fit of the coincident spectrum is required. This fit is scaled down and inserted into the anticoincident fits. The scaling down parameter is deduced from the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 1$ peak. The ratio of the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 1$ amplitude in the anticoincident fit to the amplitude in coincident fit is 1.5%. However, while changing this parameter up to 5%, no change in the final

Figure 4.16: The general function used for fitting a single peak as presented in Equation 4.3.

results has been seen. Using this parameter, a fit of the coincident area will be inserted to all the anticoincident fits. A rough fit is sufficient due to its small effect on the anticoincident spectrum, the fit is presented in Figure 4.17. This fit includes 3 peaks: 1 beryllium and 2 oxygen. They all share the same tail parameters, and the oxygen peaks share the Gaussian and Lorentzian parameters. Overall - 16 free parameters. Different models are suggested for the anticoincident spectrum, they are described in a list, shown in Figure 4.18 and their results are summarized in Table 4.1.

Figure 4.17: Rough fit of the beryllium peak. The fit includes the beryllium and the two oxygen peaks using 16 parameters, resulting in $\chi_r^2 = 1.06$.

Using these fit results, there are 4 variations of fitting the anticoincident spectrum. This spectrum in the region of interest includes 2 peaks of Lanthanum, 2 peaks of

Figure 4.18: Fits of anticoincident spectrum with decreasing degrees of freedom. The degrees of freedom noted as N and the χ_r^2 -value in the title of each subplot. The fit is on a wider domain and smaller bins than presented.

barium, and a small Americium peak.

1. Figure 4.18-1: shows a fit that uses the Γ parameter known from literature [36] for the Barium and Lanthanum peaks, taken 0 for the Americium. The Lanthanum peaks and the Americium share tail parameters, and the Barium peaks share other tail parameters. Overall - 26 parameters.
2. Figure 4.18-2: shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. The peaks now share σ and tail parameters over the whole domain. Overall - 17 parameters.
3. Figure 4.18-3: shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. This fit includes assumption of the known literature values [28] for the energy differences: $\text{La}_{K \rightarrow L2} - \text{La}_{K \rightarrow L3}$, $\text{Am} - \text{La}_{K \rightarrow L3}$ and $\text{Ba}_{K \rightarrow L2} - \text{Ba}_{K \rightarrow L3}$. Overall - 14 parameters.
4. Figure 4.18-4: shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. Here, the step parameter is not included in the tails (i.e, set to zero). Overall - 13 parameters.

The fit results and uncertainties are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Fit parameters for the anti-coincident spectrum. Several fits are considered here corresponding to the fits plotted in Figure 4.18 and parameter definitions presented in Eq. 4.3. Uncertainties are given in parentheses and calculated using the SATLAS fitter [37]. Table entries without uncertainties were set to a constant. Colored entries marked with " were set equal to the first colored value of the same color. Centroid entries marked with colored * are set with constant energy difference from the colored centroid with the same color taken from [28]. The Γ_L are set to a constant value taken from [36]. The Be groups are based on the fit-results from Figure 4.17.

Group	Parameter	Fit 1	Fit 2	Fit 3	Fit 4
BaKL2	A	231(4)	228(3)	228(3)	229(3)
	E_0	31817.2(4)	31817.3(3)	*	*
	Γ_G	22.2(8)	22.5(4)	22.5(4)	22.5(4)
	Γ_L	16.8	16.8	16.8	16.8
BaKL3	A	420(7)	418(5)	418(5)	419(5)
	E_0	32193.8(4)	32193.9(3)	32193.9(3)	32193.9(3)
	Γ_G	22.7(6)	"	"	"
	Γ_L	16.5	16.5	16.5	16.5
Tails Ba	f_{voigt}	0.86(3)	0.87(2)	0.87(2)	0.87(2)
	$f_{\text{lt}}/f_{\text{rt}}$	2.10(66)	1.74(42)	1.74(42)	1.87(44)
	b_{rt}	21.6(1.8)	24.2(1.7)	24.2(1.7)	23.7(1.6)
	$b_{\text{lt}}/b_{\text{rt}}$	2.1(3)	1.91(18)	1.92(18)	1.99(19)
	f_{step}	unconverged	1.3(3)e-4	1.3(3)e-4	0
LaKL2	A	153(3)	155(2)	155(2)	155(2)
	E_0	33035.1(4)	33035.2(3)	*	*
	Γ_G	23(1)	"	"	"
	Γ_L	17.6	17.6	17.6	17.6
Am33	A	4.0(8)	3.8(5)	3.8(5)	3.7(5)
	E_0	33196(2)	33196(2)	*	*
	Γ_G	19.7(4)	"	"	"
	Γ_L	0	0	0	0
LaKL3	A	279(5)	278(4)	278(4)	278(4)
	E_0	33442.6(4)	33442.7(3)	33442.8(3)	33442.7(3)
	Γ_G	22.0(8)	"	"	"
	Γ_L	17.8	17.8	17.8	17.8
La Tails	f_{voigt}	0.87(3)	"	"	"
	$f_{\text{lt}}/f_{\text{rt}}$	1.57(55)	"	"	"
	b_{rt}	26.4(2.8)	"	"	"
	$b_{\text{lt}}/b_{\text{rt}}$	1.64(24)	"	"	"
	f_{step}	3.4(8)e-4	"	"	"
Be	A	2.549	2.549	2.549	2.549
	E_0	33392.02	33392.02	33392.02	33392.02
	Γ_G	21.3	21.3	21.3	21.3
	Γ_L	0	0	0	0
Be Tails	f_{voigt}	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.86
	$f_{\text{lt}}/f_{\text{rt}}$	1.53	1.53	1.53	1.53
	b_{rt}	24.1	24.1	24.1	24.1
	$b_{\text{lt}}/b_{\text{rt}}$	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42
	f_{step}	26.4E-4	26.4E-4	26.4E-4	26.4E-4
background		0.77(3)	0.79(3)	0.79(3)	0.86(2)

4.4.2 Coincident Fits

To fit the coincident spectrum, information about the anti-coincident one is required since the separation is not perfect. It was arbitrarily chosen to use the third fit, Figure 4.18-3. The coincident spectrum in the region of interest mainly includes the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ peak, the ${}^{16}_{\mu}\text{O} : 4 \rightarrow 2$ peaks and remainders from the anticoincident spectrum. To fit the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ peak, it was required to take into account the fine (FS) and hyperfine structure (HFS) of the peak. The HFS calculation brought up 10 peaks, summarised in table 2.1. Each of these peaks is fitted with the full hypermet function from equation 4.3 sharing the same values for Γ_G, Γ_L and the A and E_0 are calculated from one value using the intensity and the relative position from table 2.1. Several fits are suggested for the coincident spectrum, each differs by the amount of degrees of freedom. The different models are described in a list, they are shown in Figure 4.19 and their results are summarized in Table 4.2.

- Figure 4.19-A shows a fit that uses the tail parameters taken from Figure 4.18-3, lorentzian parameter Γ_L set to zero for the muonic peaks. The barium and lanthanum shape parameters are taken from Figure 4.18-3, and the amplitudes are fitted besides the $\text{La} : K \rightarrow L3$, which overlaps with the beryllium. Its amplitude is using the amplitude of $\text{La} : K \rightarrow L2$ conserving the same ratio already fitted in Figure 4.18-3. Overall - 11 parameters are used.
- Figure 4.19-B - shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. Here, one amplitude parameter for the anticoincident spectrum. Overall - 9 parameters.
- Figure 4.19-C - shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. Here, opening the step parameter for all peaks. Overall - 10 parameters.
- Figure 4.19-D - shows the next fit variation that's based on the previous one. Here, using MuDirac [38] calculated difference for the distance between the 2 oxygen peaks: $\Delta E(N_5 \rightarrow L_3 - N_4 \rightarrow L_2) = 36.44\text{eV}$. Overall - 9 parameters.

Figure 4.19: Fits of coincident spectrum with decreasing degrees of freedom. The degrees of freedom noted as N and the χ_r^2 -value in the title of each subplot. Red: fitted line for the beryllium $2p \rightarrow 1s$ complete HFS structure with tails. Green: remainder of the lanthanum. Yellow: muonic oxygen. Black: background constant and the step function. The fit is on a wider domain and smaller bins than presented.

Table 4.2: Fit parameters for the coincident spectrum. Several fits are considered here corresponding to the fits plotted in Figure 4.19 and parameter definitions presented in Eq. 4.3. Uncertainties are given in parentheses and calculated using the SATLAS fitter [37]. Table entries without uncertainties were set to a constant. Colored entries marked with " were set equal to the first colored value of the same color. Centroid entries marked with colored * are set with constant energy difference from the colored centroid with the same color. The energy difference was calculated using MuDirac [38]. The Γ_L are set to zero for muonic peaks. The Barium and Lanthanum remainders parameters are based on fit-3 from Table 4.1.

Group	Parameter	Fit A	Fit B	Fit C	Fit D
Be	A	172(4)	171(4)	171(3)	171(3)
	E_0	33391.9(2)	33391.9(2)	33391.9(2)	33391.9(2)
	Γ_G	21.1(4)	21.18(42)	21.28(42)	21.28(42)
	Γ_L	0	0	0	0
O	A	0.8(2)	0.8(2)	1.0(3)	1.0(3)
	E_0	33586(4)	33586(4)	33586(3)	33587(2)
	Γ_G	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87
	Γ_L	0	0	0	0
O2	A	0.9(2)	0.9(2)	1.1(3)	1.1(3)
	E_0	33623(3)	33623(3)	33624(3)	*
	Γ_G	"	"	"	"
	Γ_L	0	0	0	0
BaKL2	A	5.2(4)	5.2(4)	5.2(4)	5.2(3)
	E_0	31817.3	31817.3	31817.3	31817.3
	Γ_G	22.6	22.6	22.6	22.6
	Γ_L	16.8	16.8	16.8	16.8
BaKL3	A	8.8(5)	8.8(3)	8.6(3)	8.6(3)
	E_0	32193.9	32193.9	32193.9	32193.9
	Γ_G	22.6	22.6	22.6	22.6
	Γ_L	16.5	16.5	16.5	16.5
LaKL2	A	2.8(2)	"	"	"
	E_0	33035.0	33035.0	33035.0	33035.0
	Γ_G	22.6	22.6	22.6	22.6
	Γ_L	17.6	17.6	17.6	17.6
LaKL3	A	"	"	"	"
	E_0	33442.8	33442.8	33442.8	33442.8
	Γ_G	22.6	22.6	22.6	22.6
	Γ_L	17.8	17.8	17.8	17.8
Tails	f_{voigt}	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87
	$f_{\text{lt}}/f_{\text{rt}}$	1.74	1.74	1.74	1.74
	b_{rt}	24.2	24.2	24.2	24.2
	$b_{\text{lt}}/b_{\text{rt}}$	1.92	1.92	1.92	1.92
	f_{step}	1.28e-4	1.28e-4	9.5(9)e-4	9.5(9)e-4
Background		0.27(1)	0.27(1)	0.17(1)	0.17(1)

4.4.3 Fits Summary

After having already fitted the coincident and anticoincident, it is possible to turn to the energy difference between the calibration peak $\text{La} : K \rightarrow L3$ and ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$:

$$\Delta E = E_0(\text{La:KL3}) - E_0(\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1); \sigma_{\Delta E} = \sqrt{\sigma_{E_0:\text{La}}^2 + \sigma_{E_0:\text{Be}}^2} \quad (4.4)$$

This energy difference is measured through several combinations of the anticoincidence fits presented in Figure 4.18 and the coincidence fits presented in Figure 4.19, and it is shown in Figure 4.20. The results produce different values for the energy difference, with decreasing uncertainty as the fits become more constrained. The values vary in such a way that the energy difference is the same within the boundaries of the statistical uncertainty. For this reason, it is believed that the peak lineshape shares the same parameters, and thus the most constrained fit assumptions are valid.

Figure 4.20: The calculated difference between the $\text{La} : K \rightarrow 3$ and the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ from the various combination of the anticoincidence fits (1-4) and the coincidence fits (A-B) with their order representing decreasing amount of free-parameters in their fit so that 4 and B are the most constrained fits.

Step 5: Final Calibration

In Figure 4.20, it is shown that the result for the energy difference between the $\text{La} : K \rightarrow 3$ and the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ extracted for the considered fits is the same value within the limits of the statistical uncertainty. Thus, the most constrained fit is fit 4B, but it applies a different response function of the detector for different peaks. So, it is most plausible to calculate the result after calibration using the fit 3B.

After taking into account the nonlinearity of the detector in previous chapters, the calibration should be a linear scaling. Using the La : $K \rightarrow 3$ literature value [28]: 33442.12(27)eV , the energy difference can be scaled as a conversion to eV and thus the centroid of the ${}^9_{\mu}\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ can be calculated. In these levels of precision, it's worth taking into account the photon-recoil effect [footnote for the equation]. For the measured energy from the fits 3B of 33391.26(43)eV the effect is $\delta E = -66$ meV:

$$E_{\mu\text{Be}:2\rightarrow 1}^9 = 33391.20(43)\text{eV}$$

Compared to the previously measured value [29] $E_{\mu\text{Be}:2\rightarrow 1}^9 = 33402(10)\text{eV}$, the result of this work is 1σ lower. More importantly, it is 23 times more accurate.

4.5 Preliminary radius extraction

Extracting a reliable, model-independent radius from the energy requires better theoretical descriptions and further calculations by the nuclear theorists. However, in the meantime, we may employ the process for radius calculation that is described by Fricke in [6]. We use the relation $r_{\text{new}} = r_{\text{old}}[1 - \frac{C_z \Delta E_{\text{exp}}}{R_{k\alpha, \text{old}}}]$, Where $R_{k\alpha}$ is the model-independent Barrett equivalent radius, $C_z = dR_{k\alpha}/dE$ is the sensitivity factor, and ΔE_{exp} is the difference between the theoretical result of the model and the measured value of this thesis. The resulting preliminary radius is:

$$r_c({}^9\text{Be}) = 2.565(7)\text{fm}.$$

We again mention that nuclear theory calculations by several groups are ongoing and may shift this value by 1 to 2 standard deviations.

Using the preliminary charge radius determined in this work, together with the isotope shifts measured in [39], the charge radii of the entire beryllium isotope chain can be extracted. The updated radii, along with the two contributing uncertainty components, are presented in Figure 4.22. These components correspond to the uncertainty arising from the isotope-shift measurements and the uncertainty propagated from the newly determined ${}^9\text{Be}$ reference charge radius. It can be observed that the isotope-shift contribution is slightly larger than the reference-radius contribution.

Figure 4.21: Charge radius of ^9Be from various measurements: electron scattering in 1972 [40] and 1973 [41], with the 1972 result subsequently revised to the value indicated by the blue bar [11]; muonic spectroscopy [29]; and the present thesis result.

Figure 4.22: Charge radius of the beryllium isotopes as extracted from the isotope shift measurements [39] this work's reported result of the ^9Be reference radius. Error bars are based on the isotope shift uncertainty only. The additional systematic uncertainty caused by the ^9Be reference radius as measured in this work is indicated by the gray area.

Chapter 5

Summary and outlook

The energies of low-lying muonic transitions, especially the $2p \rightarrow 1s$ line, are highly sensitive to nuclear-size effects. Measuring this transition with high precision, therefore, provides direct access to the charge radius, a key quantity for testing and constraining nuclear models. While electronic spectroscopy, scattering experiments, and muonic spectroscopy together form the global dataset on nuclear radii, a precision gap remains for several light nuclei. Closing this gap is the goal of the QUARTET collaboration.

During the 2024 QUARTET campaign, muonic lithium, beryllium, and boron were measured at PSI using a custom-built MMC detector optimized for this energy range. My thesis focuses on the analysis and extraction of results for muonic ${}^9\text{Be}$ from start to finish. It documented the preparation of the experiment, the detector operation, the data-acquisition procedures, and, in particular, the development of an analysis pipeline tailored to the specific challenges of the beam environment. Operating the MMC array in the accelerator hall introduced complications, including fluxes of highly energetic Michel electrons and the presence of external magnetic fields. These effects impacted the stability of the detector due to temperature excursions and electronic discontinuities. To mitigate these issues, a dedicated sequence of data-quality cuts and a refined temperature-correction method was implemented. The correction was segmented in time to accommodate a non-correctable electronic jump, and the combined set of cuts significantly improved both the resolution and stability.

After stabilizing the data, a series of steps: pixel-wise time alignment, nonlinear gain correction, and spectrum folding; were applied to ensure that all pixels contributed coherently to the final spectrum. This enabled a global line-shape analysis in which a uniform model was fitted to all the large peaks. The resulting measurement of the muonic-beryllium $2p \rightarrow 1s$ transition is as follows:

$$E_{2p \rightarrow 1s} = 33391.2(4)\text{eV}, \quad (5.1)$$

achieves a significant 25-fold reduction in uncertainty compared with the best previous measurement. Using a preliminary extraction method, this transition energy already improves the ${}^9\text{Be}$ charge-radius uncertainty by a factor of four. The final radius result

will be provided once our collaborators from nuclear theory finish their calculations.

Once combined with precise isotope-shift measurements from laser spectroscopy, this result was propagated to the radii of the other beryllium isotopes. Further improvement in the chain is currently limited by the isotope-shift measurements, which motivates new, more precise laser-spectroscopy experiments. In particular, the improved ${}^9\text{Be}$ radius anchors the extraction of the ${}^7\text{Be}$ radius via the ${}^7\text{Be}$ - ${}^9\text{Be}$ isotope shift, enabling more precise comparisons between mirror nuclei and tests of isospin-symmetry breaking. This comparison can be observed in Figure 5.1. Ample data in muonic Li was taken by the QUARTET collaboration, which is expected to result in a significant improvement of the ${}^7\text{Li}$ soon. Similarly, connecting ${}^9\text{Be}$ to the halo nucleus ${}^{11}\text{Be}$ via isotope shifts strengthens the constraints on halo-structure models and the asymmetry dependence of charge radii across the neutron-rich beryllium chain.

Looking ahead, several paths exist for further improvements in future beryllium measurements. Although MMC detectors have already demonstrated performance that exceeds what was achieved in the 2024 campaign, the present measurement was not limited by detector resolution or statistics. The dominant source of uncertainty originates instead from the calibration reference: lanthanum K'_α s. Despite their close proximity to the beryllium peak, their absolute energies carry uncertainties inherited from earlier measurements. Reducing the uncertainty of these calibration lines would directly enhance the precision of the extracted ${}^9\text{Be}$ charge radius. Beyond this, a refined calibration strategy involving multiple reference transitions may be effective.

In summary, this thesis establishes both the experimental feasibility and the analysis framework for high-precision muonic-atom spectroscopy with MMC detectors. The demonstrated performance positions the QUARTET program to deliver a new generation of benchmark charge-radius measurements across the light-nuclei region, providing stringent new tests for modern ab-initio nuclear theory.

Figure 5.1: Left: Mirror-difference charge radii against the isospin asymmetry from ab initio calculations in a light-blue band. Experimental values presented in red with this work's improvement of the ${}^7\text{Li}$ - ${}^7\text{Be}$ pair in blue. Right: The uncertainty contribution terms of the ${}^7\text{Li}$ - ${}^7\text{Be}$ pair with the update of the ${}^9\text{Be}$ charge radius is depicted in blue. IS presents isotope shift.

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Appendix 1: Materials

Table 1.1: Contamination sheet for PF-60 Beryllium window from Materion

Compound	Maximum %	Compound	Maximum %
Beryllium Oxide	0.8	Lead	0.002
Aluminum	0.05	Lithium	0.0003
Boron	0.0003	Magnesium	0.049
Cadmium	0.0002	Manganese	0.01
Calcium	0.01	Molybdenum	0.002
Carbon	0.06	Nickel	0.02
Chromium	0.01	Nitrogen	0.03
Cobalt	0.001	Silicon	0.04
Copper	0.01	Silver	0.001
Iron	0.08		

Appendix 2: Peak Identification

This appendix presents an overview of the peaks observed in the measured energy spectrum after the entire data-analysis process reported in Chapter 4. The identification of the measured peaks, particularly those relevant for muonic transitions, calibration, and detector-related effects, is critical to confirming the understanding of the measurement. Understanding the spectrum and having strong confidence in the measured data is crucial for reporting a high-precision result. The spectrum presented throughout this thesis is divided into two parts based on the timing with the incident muon using a scintillator trigger: coincidence and anti-coincidence regions. This way of presentation is useful since muonic-induced peaks appear mostly in the coincident spectrum, while the calibration sources appear mostly in the anti-coincident spectrum. Peak identification was performed through a combination of theoretical predictions (MuDirac calculations) of the peaks together with a review of previous measurements reported in the literature. Notably, muonic transitions of beryllium, oxygen, carbon, and nitrogen are present alongside X-ray fluorescence of barium and lanthanum, as well as the photon-emitting radioactive sources of ^{55}Fe and ^{241}Am . The detector's structural material also induces x-rays from copper and gold escape peaks originating from the detector's chamber and absorber. No explicit background subtraction was performed, as most of the peaks of interest are clearly visible above the baseline. The following table summarizes the identified peaks in the coincidence spectrum. Only approximate energy is given for the good understanding of the spectrum, while focus is placed on identification and systematic appearance.

A similar approach was applied to the anti-coincidence spectrum, which contains peaks from calibration sources (Americium-241, Lanthanum, Barium, Iron-55), corresponding escape features, and non-muonic X-rays. Unassigned or unexpected peaks are also noted for further investigation.

Figure 2.1 displays the measured spectrum with annotated peaks corresponding to the entries in the tables above. The spectrum demonstrates the successful identification of muonic and non-muonic features, thereby supporting the overall understanding of the experimental setup and its response.

In summary, the analysis presented here provides a systematic identification of the main spectral features observed in the experiment, laying the groundwork for further scientific interpretation.

Table 2.1: Identified peaks in the coincidence spectrum, grouped by material origin. Note only K_{α_1} of $\mu\text{C} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ and $\mu\text{O} : 2 \rightarrow 1$ are visible. The K_{α_2} is expected to be half of the K_{α_1} of carbon is below the $\mu\text{Be} : 4 \rightarrow 2$ line and oxygen's is expected to be too low.

Assignment	Comments	Approximate Energy (keV)
Beryllium (Target)		
$\mu\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1$	Peak of Interest	33.4
$\mu\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1 - \text{Au:L}_{\alpha}$	Escape	23.6
$\mu\text{Be} : 2 \rightarrow 1 - \text{Au:L}_{\beta}$	Escape	22.0
$\mu\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 1$	Trigger alignment	39.6
$\mu\text{Be} : 4 \rightarrow 1$		41.8
$\mu\text{Be} : 5 \rightarrow 1$		42.9
$\mu\text{Be} : 6 \rightarrow 1$		43.4
$\mu\text{Be} : 3 \rightarrow 2$	Trigger alignment	6.1
$\mu\text{Be} : 4 \rightarrow 2$		8.3
$\mu\text{Be} : 5 \rightarrow 2$		9.2
$\mu\text{Be} : 6 \rightarrow 2$		9.8
$\mu\text{Be} : 4 \rightarrow 3$		2.2
Oxygen (Target holder)		
$\mu\text{O} : 2 \rightarrow 1$		130
$\mu\text{O} : 2 \rightarrow 1 - \text{Au:K}_{\alpha_1}$	Escape	64
$\mu\text{O} : 3 \rightarrow 2$		25.0
$\mu\text{O} : 4d_{5/2} \rightarrow 2p_{3/2}$		33.6
$\mu\text{O} : 4d_{3/2} \rightarrow 2p_{1/2}$		33.6
$\mu\text{O} : 4 \rightarrow 3$		9.0
$\mu\text{O} : 5 \rightarrow 3$		13.0
$\mu\text{O} : 5 \rightarrow 4$		4.2
Nitrogen (Target holder)		
$\mu\text{N} : 2 \rightarrow 1$		103
$\mu\text{N} : 3 \rightarrow 1$		125
$\mu\text{N} : 3 \rightarrow 2$		19.0
$\mu\text{N} : 4 \rightarrow 2$		25.5
$\mu\text{N} : 5 \rightarrow 2$		29.0
Carbon (Target holder)		
$\mu\text{C} : 2 \rightarrow 1$		75
$\mu\text{C} : 2 \rightarrow 1 - \text{Au:K}_{\alpha_1}$	Escape	6.4
$\mu\text{C} : 3 \rightarrow 1$		89
$\mu\text{C} : 4 \rightarrow 1$		94
$\mu\text{C} : 5 \rightarrow 1$		96
$\mu\text{C} : 3 \rightarrow 2$		14.0
$\mu\text{C} : 4 \rightarrow 2$		19.0
$\mu\text{C} : 5 \rightarrow 4$		2.5
Copper (Chamber)		
Cu:K_{β}		8.9
Cu:K_{α}		8.0

Table 2.2: Identified peaks in the anti-coincidence spectrum, grouped by material origin. Gamma transitions are denoted as $\gamma_{n,m}$, X-rays in Siegbahn notation. Energies (keV) are taken from the NIST X-Ray Transition Energies database (Direct experimental values where available).

Assignment	Comments	Approximated energy (keV)
Americium-241 (Radioactive Source)		
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{2,0}$	Calibration	59.5
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{2,0} - \text{Au} : L\alpha_1$	Escape	49.8
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{2,0} - \text{Au} : L\beta_{1,2}$	Escape	48.0
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{4,2}$		43.4
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{1,0}$		33.2
$^{237}\text{Np} : \gamma_{2,1}$	Calibration	26.3
$^{237}\text{Np} : L\gamma's$		20-21
$^{237}\text{Np} : L\beta's$		16.0-18.5
$^{237}\text{Np} : L\alpha's$		13.8
Lanthanum (XRF target)		
La: $K\alpha_1$	Calibration	33.4
La: $K\alpha_2$	Calibration	33.0
La: $K\beta's$		37.7 – 38.0
La: $K\gamma's$		38.7 – 39.0
La: $K\alpha_1 - \text{Au} : L\alpha$	Escape	23.8
La: $K\alpha_2 - \text{Au} : L\alpha$	Escape	23.4
La: $K\alpha_1 - \text{Au} : L\beta$	Escape	21.7
Barium (XRF target)		
Ba: $K\alpha_1$	Calibration	32.1
Ba: $K\alpha_2$	Calibration	31.8
Ba: $K\beta$		36.3 – 36.6
Ba: $K\gamma$		37.2 – 37.5
Ba: $K\alpha_1 - \text{Au} : L\alpha$	Escape	22.3
Ba: $K\alpha_2 - \text{Au} : L\alpha$	Escape	22.0
Ba: $K\alpha_1 - \text{Au} : L\beta$	Escape	20.3
Ba: $K\beta - \text{Au} : L\alpha$	Escape	26.8
Iron-55 (Radioactive Source)		
Mn: $K\beta$	Calibration	6.5
Mn: $K\alpha$	Calibration	5.9
Gold (Absorber)		
Au: $L\alpha_1$		9.7
Au: $L\beta_1$		11.4
Au: $M\alpha_{1,2}$		2.12
Copper (Chamber)		
Cu: $K\alpha_1$		8.0
Cu: $K\beta_1$		8.9
Unknown/Unassigned		
25 keV unidentified	Unknown	

Figure 2.1: Measured energy spectrum after the complete analysis described in 4. Coincidence and anti-coincidence spectra are shown in red and blue correspondingly, in shaded-gray present the sum of both. From top to bottom presented spectra of certain regions: 2 – 25, 25 – 44, 44 – 62, 62 – 175 keV

Appendix 3: Jump Identification

In MMC-type detectors, the pulse information is commonly corrected with respect to the detector's temperature. In this document, this correction is also applied and described in the section 4 - Step 1. This correction was implemented by carefully choosing temperature information and amplitude information. The temperature information measured by the channel ADC1 was the most stable. However, it is susceptible to offset changes by flux-quanta, called flux-jumps, due to external magnetic field changes or highly energetic particles hitting the channels absorber. This appendix suggests a method to find flux-jumps using the other couple of temperature-sensitive channels. Each channel was cut based on a combination of higher and lower limits, as presented in Figure 4.5, to eliminate outliers, and also based on a Gaussian filter, as presented in Figure 4.6. After cleaning the channels from noise, it's safer to say that the channel's readings sample the detector's temperature. Since all three active temperature sensitive channels sample the detector's temperature, they are supposed to be correlated. An example for a couple is presented in Figure 3.1, where a correlation exists but is separated into several clusters of events. Assuming it's a behavior over time, the ratio between each pair of channels over time is supposed to show when a channel had a flux-jump. The voltage ratio for each pair of channels over time during the measurement is presented in Figure 3.2. A change in the ratio can indicate a flux-jump in one of the channels involved. Thus, this allows us to plot a figure like Figure 3.1 for all the pairs in a much shorter time, where a jump will appear. Focusing on one such suspected jump at October 11th - 3 a.m., as shown in Figure 3.3, a single offset jump is clearly presented in both the ADC25 vs. ADC1 plot and the ADC25 vs. ADC9 plot. Thus, it is most probable that ADC25 had a flux jump in this point of time.

This process can be repeated for all suspected points while focusing on looking for jumps at channel ADC1 that we use for the temperature correction process. A jump was present on October 11th around 9:30 a.m. Thus, the temperature correction process was divided into two distinct time segments and later merged back together.

Figure 3.1: The voltage readings by a couple of temperature-sensitive channels as a function of the other. Here, presented channel ADC25 as a function of channel ADC1.

Figure 3.2: The voltage readings ratios between each pair of temperature-sensitive channels over time during the beryllium measurement: ADC1, ADC9, ADC25.

Figure 3.3: An example for a focus on single suspect at October 11th - 3 a.m in a figure that's similar to 3.1. The titles' colors are consistent with 3.2